

BETWEEN WHEELS AND WORRIES: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY ON STUDENTS' TRICYCLE COMMUTING EXPERIENCE

Keith Ryan B. Belloso, Cristine S. Diocos, Winde May D. Cadayona,
Alliyah Gene T. Mapue, Mick Ian M. Cornelia, MPA

College of Arts and Sciences, Foundation University, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of Foundation University students who commute daily via pedicabs in Dumaguete City, revealing a transportation system that is both essential and deeply flawed. While tricycles remain the most accessible mode of transportation, students' heavy dependence on them exposes overlapping economic and safety vulnerabilities that turn a routine activity into a daily challenge affecting their academic performance, finances, and overall well-being. The theme "Paying Through the Nose" highlights the significant financial burden caused by fluctuating and often unreasonable fares, including overcharging and unreturned change, which foster frustration and distrust toward the transport system. Equally concerning is the psychological impact captured in the theme "Riding on Thin Ice," particularly for female commuters who face heightened risks of harassment and unsafe conditions, especially at night, prompting them to rely on constant vigilance and self-protective strategies such as sharing locations or recording plate numbers. These findings reveal a persistent gap between transportation necessity and commuter welfare, underscoring the urgent need for clearer fare regulations, stricter enforcement, improved safety measures, and gender-responsive transport policies to ensure that daily commuting does not remain a source of financial strain and emotional distress for Dumaguete's student population.

Keywords: *Dumaguete City, pedicab commuters, phenomenology, student mobility, transportation equity, tricycle commuting*

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly urbanized world, student commuting has emerged as a global issue that intersects with health, education, and social equity (World Health Organization, 2021). Once considered a mundane part of daily life, the journey to school now reflects broader patterns of inequality in mobility. Around the world, millions of students spend hours traveling each day, often in unsafe or unreliable transport systems that compromise their well-being and academic success (World Health Organization, 2021). Prolonged commutes are associated with fatigue, stress, and declining school performance—turning a simple journey into a source of vulnerability. A study by Schrank (2025) highlighted that students with longer travel times face higher risks of accidents, sleep deprivation, and reduced learning outcomes. These challenges are even more pronounced in developing cities, and dependence on informal transport systems intensifies the burden (UNESCO et al., 2021).

In the Philippine context, public transportation remains the primary mode of transport, accounting for 59.48% of trips (Galvez et al., 2025). Commuting is not merely logistical but a lived experience shaped by governance, infrastructure, and accountability. For Filipino students, daily negotiation of space, fare, and safety reveals a compromised self-determination, where access to education is entangled with disruption and resignation. Whenever these learners arrive at school, they tend to be tired and exhibit less understanding and less interaction in class discussions (Torres, 2024). Thus, public transportation commuting has been associated with higher stress levels. Longer commutes may also have a significant role in decreasing sleep quality (Evasco et al., 2025). In Dumaguete City, the "University Town," students rely heavily on pedicabs—locally known as pedicabs. Whilst the 2020 pedicab fare regulation sets official rates, "passengers report dissatisfaction with fare inconsistencies and express concerns about the affordability of tricycle transportation" (Caoleng, 2024), straining students' purchasing power and educational journey.

Despite the growing attention to public transport in national discourse, existing research on Philippine mobility primarily focuses on metropolitan contexts and major modes such as jeepneys, buses, and trains. Agaton et al. (2020) examined the socio-economic and environmental dimensions of public transport sustainability, while more recent works highlight modernization efforts like smart traffic management systems (Tariq, 2025) and digitalized mobility solutions (Shamsuddoha et al., 2025). Zulueta et al. (2024) also explored the transition toward modernized jeepneys as part of the national transport reform. Although these studies deepen the understanding of structural and technological aspects of mobility, there remains limited exploration of how daily commuting directly affects students' well-being and academic life in smaller provincial settings. Much less attention is given to cities like Dumaguete, where informal modes such as tricycles dominate daily commuting (Ablong, 2017). The researchers of this study seek to address this gap by exploring the lived experiences of Foundation University students who commute by tricycle in Dumaguete City.

Anchored on the broader vision of equitable and sustainable transportation, this study aligns with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It directly supports SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities, which emphasizes the importance of accessible, safe, and inclusive transportation systems that enhance urban mobility. It also relates to SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth, as pedicabs provide

livelihood opportunities for local drivers while simultaneously influencing the daily commuting experience of students. Furthermore, it connects to SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being since transportation directly affects physical safety, mental well-being, and the stress levels of commuters. By examining the lived experiences of Foundation University student commuters in Dumaguete City, this research reinforces the role of sustainable and fair transportation in promoting inclusive urban development. It highlights the importance of strengthening local transport policies, ensuring fare fairness, and supporting both students and drivers in achieving a balanced and equitable commuting environment.

Research Question

This qualitative inquiry, which utilized the descriptive phenomenological approach, sought to answer the universal question:

What are the lived experiences of Foundation University students as pedicab commuters in Dumaguete City?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a phenomenological research design to explore the meaning of the lived experiences of Foundation University students who commute daily via tricycles in Dumaguete City. Eight Foundation University student commuters were selected using purposive sampling for semi-structured interviews. For data analysis, the researchers of this study utilized Colaizzi's seven-step phenomenological method to systematically extract significant statements, formulate meanings, and identify emergent themes related to the students' commuting experiences.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Foundation University (FU) in Dumaguete City, where tricycles or pedicabs serve as the main mode of transportation for students moving between school, home, and nearby areas. Since many FU students rely on pedicabs for their daily commute, the university provided an appropriate setting to capture their commuting experiences and understand the broader realities of mobility and transportation in the city.

Research Participants

This study involved selected Foundation University students in Dumaguete City who regularly use pedicabs as their main mode of transportation. Using purposive sampling, the researchers chose participants who could meaningfully describe their daily commuting experiences, consistent with qualitative research standards that prioritize depth of insight over numerical representation. To be included, participants needed to be officially enrolled at FU during the study, commute primarily by pedicab, willingly share their experiences in an interview, and provide informed consent. The number of participants was kept limited to allow for richer, more detailed accounts,

with interviews continuing only until no new themes emerged, indicating data saturation. Through these criteria, the study ensured that the voices of FU student commuters accurately reflected the lived realities of youth mobility in Dumaguete City.

Research Instrument

A semi-structured interview guide served as the main tool for gathering data from Foundation University students who commute daily by pedicab. The guide contained open-ended questions designed to draw out their experiences, challenges, and perceptions as commuters, while still giving flexibility for follow-up questions. The items were developed based on the study's objectives and refined through several mock interviews to ensure clarity and alignment with the phenomenological focus. All interviews were conducted face-to-face on campus, lasted at least 25 minutes, and were audio-recorded with consent for accuracy before being transcribed verbatim.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection was carried out between September and October 2025. Before the interviews began, the researchers secured permission from Foundation University and prepared all research materials, including the interview guide and consent forms. Potential participants were identified through purposive sampling and were contacted to schedule interviews at times and locations convenient for them. Each participant was briefed about the study's purpose, confidentiality, and their right to withdraw before signing the informed consent form. The interviews used open-ended questions to explore their commuting experiences and were audio-recorded with permission, while field notes were taken to document important verbal and nonverbal cues. A reflexive journal was maintained to track the researchers' observations and potential biases. Interviews continued until no new insights emerged, ensuring that data saturation was reached.

RESULTS

After a careful analysis of the interview transcripts and codes, two major themes surfaced, reflecting the primary struggles of the student commuters: *Paying Through the Nose* and *Riding on Thin Ice*.

Major Theme 1: Paying Through the Nose

This theme reflects the financial strain experienced by Foundation University students who depend on tricycles as their primary mode of transportation. While commuting is a daily necessity, inconsistent and often excessive fare rates have made it a significant financial burden. The participants' accounts reveal how a supposedly simple journey is complicated by issues of affordability, unpredictability, and fairness, placing added pressure on students with limited allowances. This theme consists of two subthemes:

Theme 1: Money Doesn't Grow on Trees

This subtheme highlights the financial pressure brought about by the rising cost of daily commuting. Participants described the difficulty of balancing limited allowances with

increasing tricycle fares, often forcing them to make sacrifices in other aspects of their daily needs. The growing expense of transportation is not merely a practical concern but also an emotional one, contributing to stress, fatigue, and a sense of restriction in students' routines. For many, every peso matters, and each ride carries a significant financial consequence.

Participant 1 shared her experience of repeatedly commuting throughout the day, which gradually accumulates into a considerable expense:

“After class kay mo balik na sad ko PHCCI kay mo duty na pud so makahatag na pud ko, let’s say 20 or 15, so in a day if mag balik-balik ko’g ika-upat if tag 20 maka kuan ko og 80 pesos or 60 pesos ana didto. In a day sa pag commute lang.”

Trans: (After class, I go back to PHCCI because I have duty again, so I give, let’s say, ₱20 or ₱15. So, in a day, if I go back and forth four times, at ₱20 each, I spend ₱80 or ₱60, around there. Just for commuting in a day.)

Similarly, Participant 3 observed that amounts once considered sufficient are no longer adequate:

“You know, 100 pesos kanang dili na gud sya carry sa usa ka adlaw. Pliti pa na alone so like sauna, if ma- we think nga ang 100 pesos is a big kuan amount na, wala na gamay na lamang sya so if one week, 500 pesos pang pliti na lamang na, murag- no joke. Kay if ever kanang everyday ka mag work and everyday inyohang klase so like 500 a week so like kalas gyud sya dayun mahutdan gyud ka’g sinsilyo knowing nga kailangan pa nimo i-exceed or like mo hatag pa ka’g extra para ihatod ra ka.”

Trans: (You know, ₱100—that’s not enough for one whole day anymore. That’s just for the fare alone. Like before, we thought ₱100 was a big amount, but now it’s small. So, for one week, ₱500 just for the fare—that’s no joke. Because if you work everyday and you have classes every day, that’s like ₱500 a week. It’s a huge expense, and you run out of change, knowing you still need to exceed the fare or give extra just to get a ride.)

Theme 2: A Change Gone Missing

This subtheme underscores the lack of transparency and fairness in fare transactions between students and tricycle drivers. Participants frequently encountered situations involving unreturned change, inconsistent pricing, and fare manipulation—creating daily uncertainty and frustration. Although these incidents may appear minor individually, they accumulate over time, deepening the financial strain experienced by student commuters.

Participant 1 expressed discomfort when drivers failed to return her change:

“Usahay dili ko ganahan mo hatag og 20 kay naay dili mo hatag og sukli, mo direktso ra ba, kana galing ga expect ka nga ga tindog ka if dili nimo ignon kay naa man guy mga person di sila kana maulaw sila mo ingon “kuya akong sukli” kana ra gud. Mag hulat ra gyud na kana galing mo ingon- mag hulat ra gud na pag naog, kanang ibutang na gali sa zipper, dili na jud na mo sukli.”

Trans: (Sometimes I don't want to give ₱20 because some [drivers] won't give change back. They just proceed, and then you'll be standing there waiting [for the change] if you don't say anything, because there are some people who are shy to say, 'Kuya, my change.' They'll just wait, you know, they'll just wait until they step out... when [the money] is already placed in the zipper [pocket], they won't give change anymore.)

Participant 3 further described how drivers sometimes take advantage of students' lack of small bills:

“Kanang ako kay permi man gud ko mag pedicab kay kanang mag kadlawon or kanang mo adto og eskwelahan so usa pud sa problema is financial. Usahay wala man gud tay sinsilyo so og wala tay sinsilyo maka kout ta og kanang papel, oo tibouk. So mo ingon sila nga ay sometimes I feel like kuan mo take advantage sila nimo kay mo ingon sila nga ‘ay wala man koy sinsilyo’ bisag naa, of course, pedicab driver ka naa gud kay sinsilyo and then kanang if wala na silay ma sinsilyo mo ingon sila nga wala silay sinsilyo so ma forced ka nga dili nalang nimo kwaon ang sinsilyo, its either 5 pesos, 10 pesos or like 20, so ikaw nga ga dali pud ka kay you're late in class or sa imong work and then wala kay lain ma pa-sensilyoan kay they claim sad nga wala sila sinsilyo so mo ingon nalang ka ‘ay sige diha nalang na kuya’ murag ‘keep the change na lang,’ it's a red flag for me.”

Trans: (Since I always take the pedicab, especially early in the morning or when going to school, one of the problems is financial. Sometimes we don't have small change, so if we don't have small change, we end up pulling out a paper bill, a whole one. So they [drivers] say—sometimes I feel like they take advantage of you— they say they don't have change even if they do. Of course, you're a pedicab driver, you must have change. And then if they don't have change to give, they claim they don't have change, so you're forced to just leave the change, whether it's ₱5, ₱10, or like ₱20. So, since you're also rushing because you're late for class or for your work, and you have no other place to get change because they also claim they don't have any, you just say, 'Oh, never mind, kuya,' like, 'keep the change.' It's a red flag for me.)

Major Theme 2: Riding on Thin Ice

This theme reflects the lived reality of commuting students, particularly female commuters, who navigate their daily travels with fear, caution, and emotional strain. What seems like a simple routine for many becomes a psychological burden for young

women who are constantly exposed to risks of harassment and inappropriate behavior. This theme consists of two subthemes:

Theme 1: A Wolf in the Driver's Seat

This subtheme sheds light on the unsettling reality that tricycle and pedicab rides—intended for convenience—can become frightening and even traumatic experiences for female commuters.

Participant 6 shared a distressing incident when she was commuting alone at night:

“Pag unahan ana nya KIA nya naay pasulod then ni inana nako niya daan sa pag sakay nako. Pag sakay nako ni ana ko na ‘sa Maslog Elementary School ra kuya,’ nya iya unta ko i-liko sa KIA then mura na ko’g nag panic kay ngano kong iya ko i-liko didto, nya ngit-ngit na biya kaayo didto nga lugar didto ate. Para nako ate, ‘rape-on naba ko ani? Unsaon nako ani?’ ana”

Trans: (When I got on, there was a KIA in front, and he was about to turn toward it. I already told him beforehand when I got in, “Just up to Maslog Elementary School, kuya.” But then he was about to turn toward the KIA, and I started to panic — why was he turning there? It was already very dark in that area, ate. I thought to myself, “Am I going to get raped? What should I do?.”)

Similarly, Participant 2 expressed how uneasy she feels around certain pedicab drivers:

“Mao ng dili ko ganahan mag study out nga ako mo’y ipa ulahi, kay some mga halos mga pedicab driver kay mura gali, kana gali sexual kayo ilang panlantaw sa mga bayi.”

Trans: (That’s why I don’t like studying out late and being the last one to go home, because most pedicab drivers seem to look at women in a sexual way.)

Theme 2: Walking on Eggshells at Night

This subtheme captures the heightened anxiety that female students experience when commuting after dark. For many, nightfall signals not just the end of the day, but the beginning of emotional tension and constant fear of potential danger.

Participant 1 shared how nighttime commuting intensifies her vulnerability:

“If ma-gabii mahaladlok, naa gyuy kulba if magabii samot nag ako ray... kay ako raman gyud isa usually mag papauli kay ako ra man gud murag lahi ang boarding house.”

Trans: (It's scary at night, I really feel nervous if it's nighttime, especially if I'm alone... because I'm usually the only one heading home since my boarding house is in a different place (or different from others.)

Participant 5 echoed this sense of vigilance:

“Ang disadvantage ra is, tangent ra ni sya, ang disadvantage ra gyud is, especially if bayi ka, delikado gyud ka mag pa-sakay cause you don't know the driver kay what if, especially if gabii kay naa gyud koy mabantay na delikado kaayo mo sakay ang mga bayi sa gabii kay what if ang mga driver naay gamay ba, hmm? Especially imo area is sketchy. For first and foremost jud ta, naa toy, if naa man koy mga siblings na mga bayi. That's why if mag sakay mi, mas ganahan ko naa sila mga kuyog, just to be sure ra ba. Nya if ako gani, if naa koy kuyog-kuyog mga bayi, ganahan ko mag kuyog-kuyog nila og sakay, bahalag layo ilang balay cause I want to be sure nga safe lang sila. I don't want anything to happen sa mga tawo.”

Trans: (The only disadvantage is, this is just a tangent [side point]. The real disadvantage is, especially if you are a woman, it's truly dangerous to take a ride because you don't know the driver. What if, especially at night, I really observe that it's very dangerous for women to take a ride at night, because what if the drivers have ill intentions, hmm? Especially if your area is sketchy. First and foremost, if I had any female siblings, that's why if we ride, I prefer them to have companions, just to be sure. And if it's me, if I have female companions, I want to ride with them, even if their house is far, because I want to be sure that they are safe. I don't want anything to happen to people.)

DISCUSSION

Within the first major theme, Paying Through the Nose, the participants' narratives revealed the persistent financial strain experienced by Foundation University students who depend on tricycles for their daily transportation. Fluctuating and often unreasonable fare rates transformed what should be a routine commute into a continuous economic burden, marked by uncertainty and stress. Students described how inconsistent pricing forced them to constantly adjust their daily budgets, often at the expense of basic needs such as food, school materials, or savings. Similar to the findings of Caoleng (2024) and Rosal et al. (2024), tricycles were viewed as both indispensable and financially draining, particularly for students with fixed or limited allowances. The absence of standardized fare regulation heightened students' sense of vulnerability, leaving them with little control over the costs they incurred each day.

The subtheme Money Doesn't Grow on Trees further illustrated how rising transportation costs affected students beyond financial concerns. Participants emphasized that the growing expense of commuting contributed to emotional and psychological strain, including stress, fatigue, and constant worry over spending. Every trip required careful consideration, forcing students to make difficult trade-offs between transportation and other essential expenses. These experiences align with

Gumasing and Liao (2021) and Angeles et al. (2024), who noted that unregulated pricing and driver discretion disproportionately burden low-income commuters. Agustin and Fillone (2025) similarly emphasized that while tricycles are vital for urban mobility, their affordability is closely tied to commuter welfare. Supporting this, Oyegoke et al. (2021) and Igwe and Endurance (2025) found that high transportation costs contribute to academic stress and emotional exhaustion, reflecting the frustration and pressure expressed by the participants.

The subtheme A Change Gone Missing exposed issues of transparency and fairness in fare transactions between students and tricycle drivers. Participants frequently reported experiences of overcharging, unreturned change, and fare manipulation, which gradually eroded their trust in the local transport system. Although the monetary amounts involved were often small, their repeated occurrence made them significant for students managing limited resources. These findings mirror those of Ong et al. (2023) and Angeles et al. (2024), who observed that the lack of standardized fare regulation encourages informal pricing practices and weakens commuter confidence. Orpilla et al. (2024) further highlighted that weak enforcement allows such practices to persist, leaving students to comply rather than confront drivers. As noted by Rosal et al. (2024) and Gumasing and Liao (2021), these repeated losses accumulate over time, reinforcing feelings of exploitation and inequality.

In contrast, Major Theme 2: Riding on Thin Ice illuminated the emotional and psychological risks faced by female student commuters. Participants' accounts revealed that daily travel is often accompanied by fear, vigilance, and constant anticipation of danger, particularly within informal transport systems. For female students, commuting became an emotionally demanding experience shaped by gendered vulnerability rather than mere mobility. These lived experiences reflect broader patterns identified by Kacharo et al. (2022), who emphasized that women's reliance on public transportation for education and work exposes them to heightened risks. Studies by Robles et al. (2024) and Hidayati (2024) further support this, showing that a significant proportion of women experience harassment in public spaces, with transport settings being among the most common.

The subthemes A Wolf in the Driver's Seat and Walking on Eggshells at Night further underscored how fear intensifies during nighttime travel and how unchecked driver behavior deepens women's sense of insecurity. Participants described adopting defensive strategies such as avoiding night commutes, selecting specific routes, sharing locations, or ensuring companionship to reduce risk. These coping mechanisms demonstrate resilience but also reveal the burden placed on women to protect themselves in the absence of institutional safeguards. These findings align with Mchunu et al. (2025), who found that fear of harassment and assault restricts women's access to education, employment, and social participation. Locally, Rosal et al. (2024) and Orpilla et al. (2024) emphasized that weak monitoring and enforcement in informal transport systems normalize unsafe conditions, while Caoleng (2024) and Ong et al. (2023) highlighted the lack of accountability mechanisms that force women to rely on self-protection rather than formal support.

Conclusions

The experiences of Foundation University students in Dumaguete City reveal a transportation system that is both essential and deeply flawed. Tricycles remain the most accessible and reliable mode of commuting, yet they have also become a daily struggle for students. What should be a simple routine often turns into a challenge that affects their studies, finances, and overall well-being. Many students find themselves dependent on a transport system they cannot fully trust, caught between necessity and frustration.

A major concern is the heavy financial strain caused by fluctuating and often unreasonable fares. The lack of proper fare regulation leads to overcharging, unreturned change, and a growing sense of distrust toward drivers and the transport system. For many students, every ride comes with the anxiety of potential overpayment, forcing them to budget tightly and make difficult financial choices. Beyond money, the psychological toll is equally heavy—especially for female commuters who face heightened risks of harassment and unsafe conditions, particularly at night. They are often left to protect themselves through vigilance, sharing locations, or taking photos of plate numbers, highlighting the lack of systemic safety measures.

Despite these challenges—financial stress, safety concerns, and unreliable service—students continue to show remarkable patience and resilience. Many have adapted by adjusting their routines, showing empathy toward drivers, and silently enduring unfair treatment to avoid conflict. Their daily commute reflects both endurance and quiet strength amid a system in need of reform. The findings emphasize the urgent need for clearer fare regulations, improved passenger safety, and the development of alternative, more equitable transportation options for Dumaguete's student population.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

1. Develop and implement a tricycle management plan to streamline routes, reduce congestion, and ensure fair distribution across barangays.
2. Enforce driver accreditation, ID display, fare matrices, and codes of conduct with consistent sanctions for violations.
3. Require annual psychological assessments and gender-sensitivity training for drivers, alongside improved safety measures in key commuter areas.
4. Create a Transport Safety Desk under the Office of Student Services to monitor concerns and maintain records of accredited drivers.
5. Implement regular information campaigns on commuter safety, passenger rights, and appropriate conduct.
6. Strengthen collaboration with the Dumaguete City Transport Office and TODA groups to ensure fair fares, driver accreditation, and joint safety initiatives.
7. Encourage drivers to practice respectful and ethical behavior, especially toward women and minors.
8. Support driver participation in transport cooperatives or livelihood programs to reduce financial pressures and fare exploitation.
9. Require routine vehicle maintenance to ensure tricycles remain clean, safe, and

roadworthy.

10. Expand future studies to include other universities or municipalities for broader comparison and policy relevance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered strictly to established ethical standards for research involving student participants, with prior approval secured from Foundation University to ensure compliance with institutional guidelines and uphold integrity, respect, and accountability. Participation was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained after clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, benefits, and the participants' right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Interviews were conducted in safe and comfortable settings chosen by the participants, with privacy and confidentiality prioritized through respectful, semi-structured interviews that were audio-recorded only with permission and supplemented by field notes. All data were securely stored in password-protected files, anonymized using codes or pseudonyms, and validated through member checking, after which audio recordings were permanently deleted; the findings were reported truthfully and used solely for academic purposes.

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